

FREE VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE OPEN CYLINDRICAL SHELLS WITH ARBITRARY BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

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1 Introduction

Laminated composite open cylindrical shells are often encountered in aircrafts, missiles, rockets and other engineering practices. These applications have attracted a great many of researchers to develop mathematical models to predict their vibration behaviours with sufficient accuracy. The history of the vibration analysis of laminated composite open cylindrical shells can be traced back to about half a century ago and the vibration characteristics of these shells with classical boundary conditions, such as free edges (F), simply-supported supports (S) and clamped restraints (C) can be predicted precisely. Research papers and articles oriented to such contributions may be found in Quta [1], Quta and Leissa [2], Zhao et al. [3, 4], Selmane and Lakis [5], Bardell et al. [6], Zhang et al. [7], Messina and Soldatos [8-10], Lim et al. [11], Bercin [12] and so on. However the shell with more complicated boundary conditions such as elastic restraints, mix boundaries, partial supports and their combinations is still a challenge. Moreover, the existing solution procedures are often only customized for a specific set of different boundary conditions. The vibration of laminated composite open cylindrical shells with general boundary conditions is rarely studied in literature. Therefore, a general method which can be used to determine the vibration behaviours of these shells accurately and efficiently is necessary and of great significance. In this paper, a Chebyshev-Ritz method is presented for the free vibration analysis of laminated composite open cylindrical shells with general elastic boundary conditions. The displacements of the shell are generally expanded, regardless of boundary boundaries, as Chebyshev polynomial series. Several examples are given to demonstrate the accuracy and effectiveness of the current solution. The proposed solution can be readily extended to shells with nonuniform boundary supports.

2 Theoretical Formulations

2.1 Preliminaries

The model considered is shown in Fig. 1, where a orthogonal coordinate system (x, θ, z) is fixed on the middle surface of the shell. The x co-ordinate is taken in the axial direction of the shell, and the θ and z co-ordinates are, respectively, in the circumferential and radial directions. This shell is considered to be thin and of length L , mean radius R , thickness h and shallowness angle θ_0 . The linear displacements of the shell in the x , θ and z directions are denoted by u , v and w , respectively. The general boundary conditions of the shell are implemented by introducing a set of continuously distributed linear and rotational springs at each of the shell ends, and determined by the stiffness of these springs. Specifically, $k_{x0}^u, k_{x0}^v, k_{x0}^w$ and K_{x0}^w denote the set of springs distributed along the edge $x=0$. Similarly, by replacing the subscript $x0$ with $x1, \theta0$ and $\theta1$, the other three sets of continuously distributed boundary springs at corresponding ends can be denoted respectively. The classical boundary conditions can be seen as special cases of elastic support conditions. For instance, a clamped boundary condition can be generated by simply setting the stiffnesses of all the springs equal to infinite (which is represented by a very large number, 10^{12} N/m). Inversely, a free boundary is gained by setting the stiffnesses of all the springs equal to zero. In addition, the C-S-SD-F denotes a shell with champed, simply-supported, shear-diaphragm and free boundary conditions at edges $x=0, \theta=0, x=1$ and $\theta=1$, respectively. The shell is laminated by arbitrary number of liner orthotropic plies which are bonded together rigidly. The included angle between the principal direction of material axis and the x axis of the shell is denoted by β . Accordingly, the distances from the top surface and the bottom surface of the k 'th ply to the

referenced middle surface are represented by Z_{k+1} and Z_k .

On the basis of Reissner-Naghdi's theory, the strains in the middle surface and curvature changes are written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x^0 &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}, \chi_x = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ \varepsilon_\theta^0 &= \frac{\partial v}{R\partial\theta} + \frac{w}{R}, \chi_\theta = \frac{\partial}{R\partial\theta} \left(\frac{v}{R} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 w}{R\partial\theta^2} \\ \varepsilon_{x\theta}^0 &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{R\partial\theta}, \chi_{x\theta} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{v}{R} \right) - 2\frac{\partial^2 w}{R\partial x\partial\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The linear strain-displacement relations in the shell space are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x &= \varepsilon_x^0 + z\chi_x, \varepsilon_\theta = \varepsilon_\theta^0 + z\chi_\theta \\ \varepsilon_{x\theta} &= \varepsilon_{x\theta}^0 + z\chi_{x\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The constitutive equations relating the force and moment resultants to strains and curvatures of the middle surface are given in the matrix forms as [13]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_\theta \\ N_{x\theta} \\ M_x \\ M_\theta \\ M_{x\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_\theta^0 \\ \varepsilon_{x\theta}^0 \\ \chi_x \\ \chi_\theta \\ \chi_{x\theta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where N_x , N_θ and $N_{x\theta}$ represent the normal and shear force resultants. M_x , M_θ and $M_{x\theta}$ denote the bending and twisting moment resultants. A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and D_{ij} are the stretching, coupling and bending stiffness coefficients, defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^{N_L} \overline{Q_{ij}^k} (Z_{k+1} - Z_k) \\ B_{ij} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{N_L} \overline{Q_{ij}^k} [Z_{k+1}^2 - Z_k^2] \\ D_{ij} &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^{N_L} \overline{Q_{ij}^k} [Z_{k+1}^3 - Z_k^3] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

in which N_L is the amount of the plies. $\overline{Q_{ij}^k}$ denote the transformed reduced stiffness. For the k 'th orthotropic ply, the transformation stiffness matrix is defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \overline{Q_{11}^k} & \overline{Q_{12}^k} & \overline{Q_{16}^k} \\ \overline{Q_{12}^k} & \overline{Q_{22}^k} & \overline{Q_{26}^k} \\ \overline{Q_{16}^k} & \overline{Q_{26}^k} & \overline{Q_{66}^k} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}^* \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} * \mathbf{T}^T \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{T} is the transformation matrix of the k 'th ply. Q_{ij} are the constants relating stresses with strains.

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} m^2 & n^2 & -2mn \\ n^2 & m^2 & 2mn \\ mn & -mn & m^2 - n^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{1 - \mu_{12}\mu_{21}} \quad Q_{12} = \frac{\mu_{12}E_2}{1 - \mu_{12}\mu_{21}} = Q_{21} \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{22} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \mu_{12}\mu_{21}} \quad Q_{66} = G_{12}$$

where $m = \cos(\beta)$ and $n = \sin(\beta)$ are the direction coefficients of the ply. E_1 and E_2 are the Young's moduli in the principal directions, μ_{12} and μ_{21} are the corresponding Poisson's ratios. It should be noted that the Poisson's ratios are governed by equation $\mu_{12}E_2 = \mu_{21}E_1$. G_{12} is the shear modulus. An isotropic shell model can be obtained by letting $E_1 = E_2 = E$, $G_{12} = E/2(1 + \mu_{12})$.

Fig. 1. The geometry and cross-sectional view of a general elastically supported laminated composite open cylindrical shell

2.2 Energy Formulation

The potential energy of the laminated composite open cylindrical shell can be depicted as:

$$U_V = \frac{1}{2} \iint_A \left(N_x \varepsilon_x^0 + N_\theta \varepsilon_\theta^0 + N_{x\theta} \varepsilon_{x\theta}^0 + M_x \chi_x + M_\theta \chi_\theta + M_{x\theta} \chi_{x\theta} \right) dA \quad (8)$$

where A represents the mid-surface area of the shell. Substituting Eq. (1) and Eq. (3) into Eq. (8), the potential energy function of the shell can be written in terms of displacements and divided into

three components i.e. stretching strain energy (U_S), bending strain energy (U_B) and bending–stretching coupling energy (U_{SB}) [1].

The kinetic energy of the shell is given as:

$$T_k = \frac{\rho^s}{2} \int_A \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right\} dA \quad (9)$$

in which

$$\rho^s = \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \rho^k dz \right)$$

where ρ^k denotes the density of k 'th ply.

The potential energy store in the boundary springs (U_{SP}) is defined as:

$$U_{SP} = \frac{1}{2} \int_C \left\{ \begin{aligned} & [k_{x0}^u u^2 + k_{x0}^v v^2 + k_{x0}^w w^2 + K_{x0}^w \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2]_{x=0} \\ & + [k_{x1}^u u^2 + k_{x1}^v v^2 + k_{x1}^w w^2 + K_{x1}^w \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2]_{x=L} \end{aligned} \right\} dC$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} \int_L \left\{ \begin{aligned} & [k_{\theta 0}^u u^2 + k_{\theta 0}^v v^2 + k_{\theta 0}^w w^2 + K_{\theta 0}^w \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2]_{\theta=0} \\ & + [k_{\theta 1}^u u^2 + k_{\theta 1}^v v^2 + k_{\theta 1}^w w^2 + K_{\theta 1}^w \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2]_{\theta=\theta_0} \end{aligned} \right\} dL$$

2.3 Admissible Displacement Functions

In this paper, the Chebyshev polynomials of first kind are used to expand each displacement of the shell. Since these polynomials are defined on interval of [-1, 1], for simplicity and convenience in mathematical formulation, two non-dimensional parameters are introduced as following:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{x}{2L} \quad \vartheta = \frac{\theta}{2\theta_0} \quad (10)$$

The admissible displacement functions of the laminated composite open cylindrical shells can be expanded as

$$u = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} A_{mn} P_m(\varepsilon) P_n(\vartheta)$$

$$v = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} B_{mn} P_m(\varepsilon) P_n(\vartheta) \quad (11)$$

$$w = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} C_{mn} P_m(\varepsilon) P_n(\vartheta)$$

where A_{mn} , B_{mn} and C_{mn} are corresponding expanded coefficients. $P_s(\alpha)$ ($\alpha = \varepsilon, \vartheta$) are the s 'th Chebyshev polynomial of first kind which can be written in terms of cosine functions as follows:

$$P_s(\alpha) = \cos[s \arccos(\alpha)] \quad (s = 0, 1, 2, \dots) \quad (12)$$

2.4 The Solution Procedure

The Lagrangian energy function of the shell is

$$L = T_k - U_v - U_{spr} \quad (13)$$

By minimizing the total expression of the Lagrangian energy function with respect to undetermined coefficients

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \zeta} = 0 \quad \zeta = A_{mn}, B_{mn}, C_{mn} \quad (14)$$

a total of $3 * M * N$ equations related to corresponding coefficients can be achieved and summed up in matrix form as:

$$(\mathbf{K} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M}) \mathbf{G} = \mathbf{0} \quad (15)$$

in which \mathbf{K} is the stiffness matrix for the shell, where \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix. Both of them are symmetric matrixes and they can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{uu} & \mathbf{K}_{uv} & \mathbf{K}_{uw} \\ \mathbf{K}_{uv}^T & \mathbf{K}_{vv} & \mathbf{K}_{vw} \\ \mathbf{K}_{uw}^T & \mathbf{K}_{vw}^T & \mathbf{K}_{ww} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{uu} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{M}_{vv} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{M}_{ww} \end{bmatrix}$$

\mathbf{G} is the vector of expanded coefficients, is written as:

$$\mathbf{G} = [A_{00}, \dots, A_{mn}, \dots, A_{MN}, B_{00}, \dots, B_{mn}, \dots, B_{MN}, C_{00}, \dots, C_{mn}, \dots, C_{MN}]$$

The frequencies and modes of the shell can be determined easily by solving the standard characteristic equation. Each column of the eigenvector matrix is the set of coefficients for the corresponding mode. By substituting the coefficients into the Eq. (11), the displacement functions of the shell can be determined. Although Eq. (15) represents free vibration of the shell, by adding the work done by external force in Eq. (13) and summing the loading vector \mathbf{F} on the right side of Eq. (15), thus, the characteristic equation for the forced vibration of the shell is readily obtained.

3 Results and Discussion

With the theoretical formulations described in previous sections, several examples are presented in this section to illustrate the capacity and reliability of the current solution. Examples include free vibration analysis of laminated composite open cylindrical shells with different geometric and

material parameters under arbitrary boundary conditions, such as classical boundary conditions, elastic boundary conditions and their combinations. First of all, the convergence of present method is investigated and the model is checked by comparing with results presented by other researchers. Then, free vibration characteristics of these shells with various classical boundary conditions and their combinations are studied. Finally, vibrations of laminated composite shells with some types of elastic boundaries are presented. For all numerical examples, unless otherwise stated, the layers of the considered shell are made from the same material and of equal thickness.

3.1 Convergence study

Theoretically, there are infinite terms in the Chebyshev series solution. However, the series is numerically truncated and only finite terms are counted in actual calculations. Convergence study should be firstly carried out to check the calculating efficiency of the proposed method. Let us consider a four-layered angle-ply, $[-60^\circ/60^\circ/60^\circ/-60^\circ]$ completely free E-glass/epoxy open cylindrical shell. The geometric and material constants of the layers of the shell are: $L=1$ m, $R/L=2$, $\theta_0=2\arcsin(1/4)$,

$h/L=0.01$, $E_1=60.7$ GPa, $E_2=24.8$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.23$, $G_{12}=12.0$ GPa, $\rho=1700$ kg/m³. The frequency convergence of the laminated composite open cylindrical shell with respect to different truncation schemes (i.e. $M=N=5, 6, 7, \dots, 13, 14, 15$) is examined in Table 1. The first ten natural frequencies, which are expressed as dimensionless parameters as $\Omega = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho / E_2 h^2}$ are included in the table. From the table, we can see that the Chebyshev series solution has an excellent convergence, and is sufficiently accurate even when only a small number of terms are included in the series expression. In addition, it is obvious the results obtained by the present approach are in closed agreement with the existing results presented by Zhao et al. [3], Messina and Soldatos [10], Qatu and Leissa [2]. The small deviations may be caused by different shell theories and solution approaches were used in the literature. Unless otherwise stated, the truncated number of the displacement expressions will be uniformly selected as $M=N=12$ in the following discussions.

3.2 Shells with classical boundary conditions

In this subsection, the present formulation is applied to study the free vibrations of laminated composite

Table 1. Comparison of non-dimensional frequency parameters Ω for a free four-layered $[-60^\circ/60^\circ/60^\circ/-60^\circ]$ E-glass/epoxy shell ($L=1$ m, $R/L=2$, $\theta_0=2\arcsin(1/4)$, $h/L=0.1$, $E_1=60.7$ GPa, $E_2=24.8$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.23$, $G_{12}=12.0$ GPa, $\rho=1700$ kg/m³)

Terms	Modes									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
5*5	3.3040	6.0936	8.9867	11.589	13.358	22.657	24.664	26.510	28.938	32.031
6*6	3.2557	5.6463	8.5238	11.328	12.884	16.865	19.418	23.138	23.156	26.349
7*7	3.2508	5.5972	8.4045	11.171	12.552	15.759	18.424	22.806	22.834	26.089
8*8	3.2498	5.5910	8.3873	11.137	12.533	15.328	17.895	22.072	22.142	26.036
9*9	3.2498	5.5907	8.3869	11.135	12.528	15.296	17.851	22.054	22.122	26.027
10*10	3.2497	5.5906	8.3867	11.134	12.528	15.292	17.845	22.047	22.117	26.025
11*11	3.2497	5.5906	8.3867	11.134	12.528	15.292	17.845	22.046	22.117	26.025
12*12	3.2497	5.5906	8.3867	11.134	12.528	15.292	17.845	22.046	22.116	26.025
13*13	3.2497	5.5906	8.3867	11.134	12.528	15.292	17.845	22.046	22.116	26.025
14*14	3.2497	5.5906	8.3867	11.134	12.528	15.292	17.845	22.046	22.116	26.025
15*15	3.2497	5.5906	8.3867	11.134	12.528	15.292	17.845	22.046	22.116	26.025
Ref.[2]	3.2920	5.7416	8.5412	11.114	12.591	15.696	18.221	22.058	22.194	25.871
Ref.[3]	3.3016	5.7328	8.5087	11.133	12.626	15.724	18.231	22.129	22.257	25.828
Ref.[10]	3.2498	5.5910	8.3873	11.137	12.533	15.328	17.895	22.072	22.142	26.036

open cylindrical shells with classical boundary conditions. These supports can be seen as special cases of elastic boundary conditions. Different types of classical boundaries and their combinations considered in present work are realized by assigning the boundary springs at proper stiffness. Taking edge $x=0$ for example, the corresponding spring stiffness for four types of classical edges are given as follows (unless otherwise stated, N/m and N/rad are utilized as the units of the stiffness about the translational springs and rotational springs, respectively):

Free edge (F):

$$k_{x0}^u = k_{x0}^v = k_{x0}^w = K_{x0}^w = 0$$

Shear-diaphragm edge (SD):

$$k_{x0}^u = K_{x0}^w = 0, k_{x0}^v = k_{x0}^w = 10^{12}$$

Simply-supported edge (S):

$$k_{x0}^u = k_{x0}^v = k_{x0}^w = 10^{12}, K_{x0}^w = 0$$

Clamped edge (C):

$$k_{x0}^u = k_{x0}^v = k_{x0}^w = K_{x0}^w = 10^{12}$$

The first case treated is a full Shear-diaphragm supported three-layered cross-ply $[90^\circ/0/90^\circ]$ open cylindrical Shell with different thickness-radius ratios (i.e. $h/R=0.02, 0.01$). The detailed comparisons of the first six non-dimensional frequency parameters $\Omega = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho/E_1 R h}$ obtained by present approach with results reported by Zhao et al. [4] and Messina and Soldatos [8] are given in Table 2. The dimensions and material properties of the layers of the shell are given as: $L=5$ m, $R/L=1/5$, $\theta_0=\pi/3$, $E_2=2$ GPa, $E_1=25E_2$, $\mu_{12}=0.25$, $G_{12}=0.5E_2$, $\rho=1700$ kg/m³. It is obvious that the present results match were with Zhao's, the discrepancy is negligible. Although the results are slightly higher than Messina and Soldatos', the discrepancy is very

small and does not exceed 1.55% for the worst case. The small discrepancies in the results may be attributed to the different shell theories and solution approaches were used in the literature.

To further prove the validity of the present formulations for the free vibration analysis of laminated composite open cylindrical shells, Table 3 lists the first six frequencies which is expressed in terms of dimensionless parameters $\Omega = \omega s^2 \sqrt{\rho h/D}$ ($s=R\theta_0$, $D= E_1 h^3/12(1-\mu_{12}\mu_{21})$) of a full clamped four-layered, symmetric cross-ply $[\beta'/-\beta'/-\beta'/\beta']$ open cylindrical shell with various lamination schemes. The geometric and material properties are assumed to be: $L/s=1$, $h/s=0.01$, $R/h=500$, $E_2=2$ GPa, $E_1=15.4E_2$, $\mu_{12}=0.3$, $G_{12}=0.8E_2$, $\rho=1500$ kg/m³. Through comparing, it can be seen that present result match very well with result given by Bardell [6]. This study also shows that the lamination schemes influence significantly the general trend of the vibration behaviors of the shell. The $[90^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ]$ composite shell may be thought to be the stiffest one in this study.

The excellent agreement of comparison between proposed solutions with published results given in Table 1-3 indicates that the present solutions are accurate. Having gained confidence in present method, let us consider open shells with different shallow angles and boundary conditions. In Table 4, the lowest three dimensionless frequency parameters $\Omega = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho/E_2 h^2}$ of a three-layered cross-ply $[0/90^\circ/0]$ shell with various shallow angles and boundary conditions are presented. The geometric and material constants of the layers of the shell are: $L=2$ m, $R/L=0.5$, $h/L=0.01$, $E_1=25E_2$, $E_2=1$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.25$, $G_{12}=0.5E_2$, $\rho=1500$ kg/m³. It can be seen from the table that for the shell with F-F-F-F,

Table 2. Comparison of non-dimensional frequency parameters Ω for a full Shear-diaphragm restraints three-layered $[90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]$ shell ($L=5$ m, $R/L=1/5$, $\theta_0=\pi/3$, $E_2=2$ GPa, $E_1=25E_2$, $\mu_{12}=0.25$, $G_{12}=0.5E_2$, $\rho=1700$ kg/m³).

h/R	Methods	Modes					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
1/50	Present	8.314	11.582	15.970	20.656	25.430	30.222
	Ref.[4]	8.311	11.570	15.950	20.630	25.390	30.180
	Ref.[8]	8.207	11.500	15.910	20.610	25.390	30.210
1/100	Present	7.134	13.388	20.431	24.555	25.028	26.146
	Ref.[4]	7.131	13.380	20.410	24.560	25.030	26.140
	Ref.[8]	7.118	13.380	20.420	24.180	24.660	25.790

SD-SD-SD-SD, S-S-S-S, C-C-C-C and C-S-C-S boundary conditions, the frequency parameters Ω of the shell diminish as the shallow angles increased. However, an inverse tendency is seen for the shell with S-F-S-F, C-F-F-F and C-F-C-F supports conditions. The above numerical examples are presented as laminated composite open cylindrical shells with

classical boundary conditions. It is obvious that the frequency parameters for arbitrary boundary conditions can be determined easily by assigning the boundary springs with proper stiffnesses. Besides, unlike most existing method, the proposed method offers a unified solution for the entire boundary conditions

Table 3. Comparison of non-dimensional frequency parameters Ω of a full clamped laminated composite four-layered $[\beta'/-\beta'/-\beta'/\beta]$ open cylindrical shells with different lamination schemes ($L/s=1$, $h/s=0.01$, $R/h=500$, $E_2=2$ GPa, $E_1=15.4E_2$, $\mu_{12}=0.3$, $G_{12}=0.8E_2$, $\rho=1500$ kg/m³).

Modes	Lamination schemes $[\beta'/-\beta'/-\beta'/\beta]$									
	0°		30°		45°		60°		90°	
	Present	Ref.[6]	Present	Ref.[6]	Present	Ref.[6]	Present	Ref.[6]	Present	Ref.[6]
1	28.27	28.27	31.49	31.49	38.89	38.89	48.87	48.87	60.98	60.98
2	31.20	31.20	38.83	38.83	46.26	46.26	52.89	52.89	63.88	63.88
3	42.56	42.61	56.31	56.37	55.70	55.70	60.17	60.17	64.20	64.20
4	60.27	60.55	57.60	57.61	66.35	66.38	67.83	67.86	70.77	70.77
5	65.04	65.04	71.02	71.09	78.51	78.66	77.67	77.74	71.48	71.50
6	68.76	68.76	79.23	79.57	88.83	89.02	87.70	87.90	82.19	82.21

Table 4. The lowest three non-dimensional frequency parameters Ω for a three-layered cross-ply $[0/90^\circ/0]$ open cylindrical shell with various shallow angles and boundary conditions ($L=2$ m, $R/L=0.5$, $h/L=0.01$, $E_1=25E_2$, $E_2=1$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.25$, $G_{12}=0.5E_2$, $\rho=1500$ kg/m³).

Shallow angles	Modes	Boundary conditions							
		F-F-F-F	SD-SD-SD-SD	S-S-S-S	C-C-C-C	S-F-S-F	C-F-F-F	C-F-C-F	C-S-C-S
$\theta_0=45^\circ$	1	12.127	57.116	111.19	116.41	24.608	9.775	38.124	116.41
	2	46.892	104.88	150.92	168.42	40.256	14.228	50.001	168.41
	3	56.374	121.48	216.41	218.95	68.977	41.947	76.183	218.92
$\theta_0=90^\circ$	1	5.8805	57.116	72.945	80.530	30.888	14.848	42.620	80.508
	2	13.332	66.430	84.942	92.026	33.904	15.975	44.759	91.865
	3	17.670	97.130	114.53	121.58	61.097	40.258	69.697	119.75
$\theta_0=135^\circ$	1	3.6926	57.116	65.270	74.826	32.094	15.314	43.467	73.627
	2	5.5304	59.115	69.885	78.626	32.614	15.925	43.798	77.860
	3	9.0765	76.421	85.531	96.811	60.288	35.228	69.186	92.403
$\theta_0=180^\circ$	1	2.5551	56.975	62.716	73.371	32.359	15.508	43.635	71.406
	2	2.9189	57.117	64.870	78.499	32.518	15.750	43.728	73.240
	3	5.7627	66.959	75.228	102.61	60.096	34.070	69.115	82.978
$\theta_0=225^\circ$	1	1.7823	56.288	61.710	76.858	32.572	15.593	43.795	70.552
	2	1.8532	57.139	64.213	86.324	32.640	15.676	43.851	72.893
	3	4.0602	65.766	74.918	105.07	60.186	33.736	69.244	82.628

and the change of boundary conditions from one case to another is as easy as changing structure parameters.

3.3 Shells with elastic boundary conditions

Laminated composite open cylindrical Shells with elastically restrained edges are widely encountered in engineering practices. The vibration analyses of these shells are necessary and of great significance. Thus, in this subsection, the present formulation is applied to investigate the free vibration behaviors of laminated composite open cylindrical shells with elastic boundary conditions.

There are infinite types of possible combinations of elastic boundary conditions at the four edges of the open cylindrical shells, and it is impossible to undertake an all-encompassing survey of them. Three types of elastic support conditions, denoted by E^1 , E^2 and E^3 are studied in this paper. Taking edge $x=0$ for example, the corresponding spring stiffness

for the three types of specifically elastic boundaries are given as follows:

Type E^1 : only the radial direction is elastically restrained (i.e. $w \neq 0, u=v=\partial w/\partial x=0$).

$$k_{x0}^w = 2 \times 10^7, k_{x0}^u = k_{x0}^v = K_{x0}^w = 10^{12}$$

Type E^2 : both the axial and circumferential directions are elastically restrained (i.e. $u \neq 0, v \neq 0, w = \partial w/\partial x=0$).

$$k_{x0}^u = k_{x0}^v = 2 \times 10^7, k_{x0}^w = K_{x0}^w = 10^{12}$$

Type E^3 : the axial, circumferential and radial directions are elastically restrained (i.e. $u \neq 0, v \neq 0, w \neq 0, \partial w/\partial x=0$).

$$k_{x0}^u = k_{x0}^v = k_{x0}^w = 2 \times 10^7, K_{x0}^w = 10^{12}$$

The first case treated is about certain elastically restricted two-layered, cross-ply open cylindrical shells with elastic boundary conditions. In Table 5, the lowest three dimensionless frequency parameters $\Omega = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho/E_2 h^2}$ of the considered open cylindrical

Table 5. The lowest three dimensionless frequency parameters Ω for certain two-layered cross-ply open cylindrical shells with six types of classical and elastic combined boundary conditions ($L=5$ m, $s/L=1$, $h/L=0.01$, $E_1=20E_2$, $E_2=5$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.27$, $G_{12}=0.55E_2$, $\rho=1650$ kg/m³).

L/R	Lamination schemes	Modes	Boundary conditions					
			E^1 -F- E^1 -F	E^2 -F- E^2 -F	E^3 -F- E^3 -F	E^1 -C- E^1 -C	E^2 -C- E^2 -C	E^3 -C- E^3 -C
5	[0/90°]	1	55.3724	46.0535	42.9583	116.547	106.012	77.5923
		2	56.3150	47.9456	44.0587	124.592	113.021	79.5871
		3	96.3661	83.1294	72.4381	151.788	142.554	91.9835
	[90°/0]	1	56.0530	46.4023	43.2628	119.765	110.020	79.0919
		2	57.0080	48.1510	44.1441	129.792	117.855	80.2836
		3	97.4022	83.4210	73.5144	153.762	145.963	95.3742
0.1	[0/90°]	1	14.1517	14.2126	14.0876	29.9821	29.9396	29.7156
		2	14.3418	14.2160	14.0931	32.1436	32.1960	32.1211
		3	21.4165	21.5161	21.3328	47.4091	48.1065	47.3767
	[90°/0]	1	14.1393	14.1176	13.9974	25.8503	25.9103	25.8406
		2	14.2762	14.1966	14.0721	28.3362	28.4384	28.3192
		3	21.4029	21.5322	21.3486	42.5613	43.2518	42.5300
0 ($R=\infty$)	[0/90°]	1	12.9261	13.0196	12.9246	16.1172	16.2189	16.1151
		2	13.8785	13.9966	13.8770	28.4736	28.5666	28.4353
		3	21.0473	21.2112	21.0420	37.3825	38.1869	37.3802
	[90°/0]	1	12.9261	13.0196	12.9246	16.1172	16.2189	16.1151
		2	13.8785	13.9966	13.8770	28.4736	28.5667	28.4353
		3	21.0473	21.2112	21.0424	37.3825	38.1869	37.3802

Table 6. The lowest two dimensionless frequency parameters Ω for a three-layered, cross-ply [0/90°/0] composite open cylindrical shell with various elastic boundary conditions ($L=2$ m, $R/L=0.5$, $\theta_0=\pi/4$, $h/L=0.01$, $E_1=20E_2$, $E_2=5$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.27$, $G_{12}=0.55E_2$, $\rho=1650$ kg/m³).

Spring stiffness	k_{x1}^u		k_{x1}^v		k_{x1}^w		K_{x1}^w	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
0	5.257	6.548	5.257	6.548	5.257	6.548	5.257	6.548
10 ¹	5.257	6.548	5.257	6.548	5.257	6.548	5.257	6.548
10 ²	5.257	6.548	5.257	6.548	5.258	6.548	5.258	6.548
10 ³	5.257	6.548	5.258	6.548	5.261	6.550	5.259	6.548
10 ⁴	5.257	6.548	5.259	6.548	5.295	6.573	5.269	6.551
10 ⁵	5.257	6.548	5.277	6.550	5.620	6.792	5.364	6.578
10 ⁶	5.258	6.548	5.450	6.577	8.036	8.557	5.924	6.752
10 ⁷	5.262	6.548	6.824	6.889	14.454	15.124	6.668	7.011
10 ⁸	5.306	6.549	8.628	12.925	17.524	18.297	6.847	7.079
10 ⁹	5.643	6.564	13.911	17.842	17.937	18.667	6.867	7.086
10 ¹⁰	6.501	6.628	16.505	18.562	17.990	18.705	6.869	7.087
10 ¹¹	6.679	6.873	16.916	18.641	17.998	18.709	6.869	7.087
10 ¹²	6.689	6.924	16.993	18.652	17.999	18.709	6.869	7.087
10 ¹³	6.689	6.924	16.993	18.652	17.999	18.709	6.869	7.087
10 ¹⁴	6.689	6.924	16.993	18.652	17.999	18.709	6.869	7.087

Table 7. The lowest two dimensionless frequency parameters Ω for a three-layered, cross-ply [0/90°/0] composite open cylindrical shell with various elastic boundary conditions ($L=2$ m, $R/L=0.5$, $\theta_0=\pi/4$, $h/L=0.01$, $E_1=20E_2$, $E_2=5$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.27$, $G_{12}=0.55E_2$, $\rho=1650$ kg/m³).

Spring stiffness	k_{x1}^u		k_{x1}^v		k_{x1}^w		K_{x1}^w	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
0	24.128	25.063	24.255	25.832	21.691	24.601	18.409	20.616
10 ¹	24.128	25.063	24.255	25.832	21.691	24.601	18.409	20.616
10 ²	24.128	25.063	24.255	25.832	21.691	24.601	18.409	20.616
10 ³	24.128	25.063	24.255	25.832	21.691	24.601	18.411	20.617
10 ⁴	24.128	25.063	24.255	25.832	21.692	24.601	18.426	20.629
10 ⁵	24.128	25.063	24.255	25.832	21.696	24.602	18.571	20.749
10 ⁶	24.128	25.063	24.255	25.832	21.74	24.615	19.707	21.705
10 ⁷	24.128	25.065	24.255	25.832	22.111	24.723	22.75	24.414
10 ⁸	24.13	25.076	24.255	25.832	23.399	25.236	24.061	25.655
10 ⁹	24.142	25.174	24.255	25.836	24.134	25.731	24.235	25.824
10 ¹⁰	24.196	25.541	24.255	25.842	24.243	25.831	24.253	25.842
10 ¹¹	24.244	25.794	24.255	25.844	24.254	25.842	24.255	25.844
10 ¹²	24.254	25.839	24.255	25.844	24.255	25.844	24.255	25.844
10 ¹³	24.254	25.839	24.255	25.844	24.255	25.844	24.255	25.844
10 ¹⁴	24.254	25.839	24.255	25.844	24.255	25.844	24.255	25.844

shells with three different length-radius ratios ($L/R=5, 0.1, 0$) are presented, in which six types of classical and elastic combined boundary conditions are included. The shells are assumed to be made from composite lamina with following properties: $L=5$ m, $s/L=1$, $h/L=0.01$, $E_1=20E_2$, $E_2=5$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.27$, $G_{12}=0.55E_2$, $\rho=1650$ kg/m³. From the table, it can be seen that the natural frequency of the shells decreased with the length radius ratio get large. In addition, it is obvious that for length-radius ratio $L/R=5, 0.1$, the corresponding mode frequency parameters for shells with $[0/90^\circ]$ lamination schemes are different from the $[90^\circ/0]$ case, while, for $L/R=0$ (it can be seen as plate), the corresponding mode frequency parameters for these two lamination schemes are equal to each other.

In next numerical example, the effect of the elastic boundary conditions on the natural vibration frequencies of the shells will be studied in detail. Assume that a three-layered, cross-ply $[0/90^\circ/0]$ composite open cylindrical shell is simply supported in edge $x=0$, free in edge $\theta=0$, $\theta=\theta_0$, and elastically restrained by only one kind of spring components in edge $x=L$ ($k_{x1}^u, k_{x1}^v, k_{x1}^w$ and K_{x1}^w , respectively). In Table 6, the lowest two frequency parameters $\Omega = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho/E_2 h^2}$ for the shell with different elastically restrained stiffnesses are listed. The material and geometric properties of the layers of the shell are given as: $L=2$ m, $R/L=0.5$, $\theta_0=\pi/4$, $h/L=0.01$, $E_1=20E_2$, $E_2=5$ GPa, $\mu_{12}=0.27$, $G_{12}=0.55E_2$, $\rho=1650$ kg/m³. It is obvious that when the shell is only elastically restrained by axial liner springs k_{x1}^u there is little variation in frequency parameters as the stiffness of springs increasing from 0 to 10^{14} . The similar tendency is seen for the shell only restrained by rotation springs K_{x1}^w . However, when the shell is elastically supported by circumferential and radial liner springs, respectively, with the stiffness of the springs increasing from 0 to 10^7 , there is no effect on frequency parameters of the shell. As the stiffness further increase, a distinct influence can be observed, in which the frequency parameters increases rapidly, when the stiffness beyond 10^{10} , the frequency parameters approaches the utmost and remain unchanged.

Last, let us consider another case. Suppose the shell model mentioned previously is simply supported in edge $x=0$, free in edge $\theta=0$, $\theta=\theta_0$ as usual, but the $x=L$ edge is supported by all the four groups of springs in which three groups of them with infinite (10^{10}) stiffness and the rest one is assigned at

changed stiffness. The lowest two frequency parameters $\Omega = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho/E_2 h^2}$ of the shell with different elastically restrained stiffnesses are presented in Table 7. Since the elastic edge are rigidly restrained by three sets of spring components. Therefore, the frequency parameters are not very sensitive to the changes of the stiffness of the rest springs.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, a Chebyshev-Ritz method has been proposed to study free vibrations of laminated composite open cylindrical shells with arbitrary boundary conditions. The energy variational principle is employed to derive the formulation based on the Reissner-Naghdi's shell theory. The displacement fields of the shell are expanded in terms of the first kind Chebyshev polynomials. The accuracy, efficiency and reliability of present method are validated and illustrated by free vibration analyses of laminated composite open cylindrical shells with different dimension and material parameters under general elastic boundary conditions. Numerical results obtained by proposed method are found in excellent agreement with the literature. The method described in this paper is believed to include several advantages: first, it is a general method which can be used to determinate the free and forced vibration behaviours of laminated composite open cylindrical open shells with arbitrary boundary conditions accurately; second, the proposed method offers a unified solution for the arbitrary supporting conditions and the change of boundary conditions from one case to another is as easy as changing structure parameters; third, it models the elastically restrained open cylindrical shells which is rarely attempted in the literature but is of practical importance; finally, the proposed solution can be readily extended to shells with nonuniform boundary supports

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Appendix A.

Detailed expressions of the stiffness matrix and the

mass matrix:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{K}_{uu} &= \frac{LR\theta_0}{4} \left(A_{11}F_{00}^{11} + \frac{A_{66}}{R^2}F_{11}^{00} + \frac{A_{16}}{R}(F_{10}^{01} + F_{01}^{10}) \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{R\theta_0}{2} \left(k_{x0}^u (-1)^{m+\bar{m}} + k_{x1}^u \right) H^{00} \\
 &\quad + \frac{L}{2} \left(k_{\theta 0}^u (-1)^{n+\bar{n}} + k_{\theta 1}^u \right) G^{00} \\
 \mathbf{K}_{uv} &= \frac{LR\theta_0}{4} \left(\frac{A_{66}}{R}F_{01}^{10} + \frac{A_{12}}{R}F_{10}^{01} + A_{16}F_{00}^{11} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{A_{26}}{R^2}F_{11}^{00} + \frac{B_{66}}{R^2}F_{01}^{10} + \frac{B_{12}}{R^2}F_{10}^{01} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{B_{16}}{R}F_{00}^{11} + \frac{B_{26}}{R^3}F_{11}^{00} \right) \\
 \mathbf{K}_{uw} &= \frac{LR\theta_0}{4} \left(\frac{A_{12}}{R}F_{00}^{01} + \frac{A_{26}}{R^2}F_{01}^{00} \right) \\
 &\quad - \frac{L\theta_0}{4} \left(B_{11}F_{00}^{21} + \frac{2B_{66}}{R}F_{11}^{10} + \frac{B_{12}}{R}F_{20}^{01} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + 2B_{16}F_{10}^{11} + B_{16}F_{01}^{20} + \frac{B_{26}}{R^2}F_{21}^{00} \right) \\
 \mathbf{K}_{vu} &= \frac{LR\theta_0}{4} \left(\frac{A_{22}}{R^2}F_{11}^{00} + A_{66}F_{00}^{11} + \frac{A_{26}}{R}(F_{10}^{01} + F_{01}^{10}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{D_{22}}{R^4}F_{11}^{00} + \frac{D_{66}}{R^2}F_{00}^{11} + \frac{D_{26}}{R^3}(F_{10}^{01} + F_{01}^{10}) \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{L\theta_0}{2} \left(\frac{B_{22}}{R^2}F_{11}^{00} + B_{66}F_{00}^{11} + \frac{B_{26}}{R}(F_{10}^{01} + F_{01}^{10}) \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{R\theta_0}{2} \left(k_{x0}^v (-1)^{m+\bar{m}} + k_{x1}^v \right) H^{00} \\
 &\quad + \frac{L}{2} \left(k_{\theta 0}^v (-1)^{n+\bar{n}} + k_{\theta 1}^v \right) G^{00} \\
 &\quad + \frac{L}{2R^2} \left(K_{\theta 0}^w (-1)^{n+\bar{n}} + K_{\theta 1}^w \right) G^{00} \\
 \mathbf{K}_{vw} &= \frac{LR\theta_0}{4} \left(\frac{A_{22}}{R^2}F_{01}^{00} + \frac{A_{26}}{R}F_{00}^{01} - \frac{D_{22}}{R^4}F_{21}^{00} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{2D_{66}}{R}F_{10}^{11} + \frac{D_{12}}{R^2}F_{01}^{20} + \frac{D_{16}}{R}F_{00}^{21} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{D_{26}}{R^3}F_{20}^{01} + \frac{2D_{26}}{R^3}F_{11}^{10} \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{L\theta_0}{4} \left(\frac{B_{22}}{R^2}F_{01}^{00} - \frac{B_{22}}{R^2}F_{21}^{00} - 2B_{66}F_{00}^{11} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - B_{12}F_{01}^{20} - RB_{16}F_{00}^{21} - \frac{2B_{26}}{R}F_{11}^{10} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{B_{26}}{R}F_{00}^{01} - \frac{B_{26}}{R}F_{20}^{01} \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{L}{\theta_0 R^2} \left(K_{\theta 0}^w n^2 (-1)^{n+\bar{n}-1} + K_{\theta 1}^w n^2 \right) G^{00} \\
 \mathbf{K}_{ww} &= \frac{LR\theta_0}{4} \left(\frac{A_{22}}{R^2}F_{00}^{00} + D_{11}F_{00}^{22} + \frac{D_{22}}{R^4}F_{22}^{00} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{4D_{66}}{R^2}F_{11}^{11} + \frac{D_{12}}{R^2}F_{02}^{20} + \frac{D_{12}}{R^2}F_{20}^{02} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{2D_{16}}{R}F_{01}^{21} + \frac{2D_{16}}{R}F_{10}^{12} + \frac{2D_{26}}{R^3}F_{12}^{10} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{2D_{26}}{R^3}F_{21}^{01} - \frac{B_{22}}{R^3}F_{02}^{00} + \frac{B_{22}}{R^3}F_{20}^{00} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{B_{12}}{R}F_{00}^{02} - \frac{B_{12}}{R}F_{00}^{20} - \frac{2B_{26}}{R^2}F_{10}^{10} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{2B_{26}}{R^2}F_{01}^{01} \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{R\theta_0}{2} \left(k_{x0}^w (-1)^{m+\bar{m}} + k_{x1}^w \right) H^{00} \\
 &\quad + \frac{L}{2} \left(k_{\theta 0}^w (-1)^{n+\bar{n}} + k_{\theta 1}^w \right) G^{00} \\
 &\quad + \frac{2R\theta_0}{L^2} \left(K_{x0}^w m^2 \bar{m}^{-2} (-1)^{m+\bar{m}} + K_{x1}^w m^2 \bar{m}^{-2} \right) H^{00} \\
 &\quad + \frac{2L}{R^2 \theta_0^2} \left(K_{x0}^w n^2 \bar{n}^{-2} (-1)^{n+\bar{n}} + K_{x1}^w n^2 \bar{n}^{-2} \right) H^{00} \\
 \mathbf{M}_{uu} &= \frac{\rho h LR \theta_0}{4} F_{00}^{00} \\
 \mathbf{M}_{vv} &= \frac{\rho h LR \theta_0}{4} F_{00}^{00} \\
 \mathbf{M}_{ww} &= \frac{\rho h LR \theta_0}{4} F_{00}^{00}
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$G^{ab} = \int_{-1}^1 \frac{2^{a+b}}{L^{a+b}} \frac{d^a P_m(\varepsilon)}{d\varepsilon^a} \frac{d^b P_m(\varepsilon)}{d\varepsilon^b} d\varepsilon$$

$$H^{ce} = \int_{-1}^1 \frac{2^{c+e}}{\theta_0^{c+e}} \frac{d^c P_n(\vartheta)}{d\vartheta^c} \frac{d^e P_n(\vartheta)}{d\vartheta^e} d\vartheta$$

$$F_{ce}^{ab} = G^{ab} H^{ce} \quad a, b, c, e = 0, 1, 2$$

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